

Track Reconstruction at the Electron-Ion Collider

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ABSTRACT

During the past year, substantial progress has been made on the design of EPIC, which is the first detector for the Electron-Ion Collider (EIC). All detector variants proposed during this phase incorporated silicon trackers for charged particle tracking and vertex reconstruction. A simulation and reconstruction framework based on DD4hep + Gaudi + Acts + EDM4hep was developed by the ATHENA proposal collaboration to demonstrate a tracking performance consistent with the EIC physics requirements as defined in the Yellow Report. In this work, the ATHENA tracking system configuration, reconstruction studies with Acts, and plans to further advance this effort for EIC Project Detector 1 are discussed.

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1 Introduction

The Electron-Ion-Collider (EIC) will be a new experimental facility to study the structure and dynamics of quarks and gluons in nucleons and nuclei. The facility will be sited at Brookhaven National Laboratory on Long Island, New York, and the U.S. Department of Energy has granted Critical Decision 1 (CD-1) for the project. In March 2021, Brookhaven National Laboratory (BNL) and Thomas Jefferson National Accelerator Facility (JLab) together issued a call for Collaboration Proposals for Detectors at the EIC [1]. According to the proposal submission guidelines, the nominal concepts proposed for EIC Detector 1 were required to satisfy the needs of the science program laid out in the EIC Community White paper [2] and the NAS Science Assessment [3], recently worked out further in the form of reference detector concepts in the EIC Yellow Report [4] with the corresponding particle identification, calorimetry, tracking and vertexing resolutions. The collaboration proposals were furthermore required to provide paths towards the construction of such a detector by CD-4A, the start of EIC accelerator operations, currently anticipated in 2031. The proposals were also to address cost, schedule, and risk.

Three proto-collaborations – ATHENA [5], ECCE [6] and CORE [7] – were formed during the detector proposal stage. There are two possible experimental halls to accommodate EIC detectors on the six and eight o'clock locations of the RHIC ring, called IP6 and IP8 respectively. CORE's design focuses on the far-forward detectors making use of the possibility of secondary focusing at IP8. ATHENA and ECCE are both designed for IP6. The latter two detector concepts have many commonalities in their proposed tracking and vertexing subsystems. ECCE opted to re-use the 1.4 T solenoid magnet from the former BaBar experiment [8], while ATHENA proposed to build a new solenoidal magnet with a 3 T field strength. During the ATHENA proposal stage, a new simulation and reconstruction framework was developed featuring modern software created by the high energy physics community, including DD4hep [9], Gaudi [10], Acts [11] and EDM4hep [12]. These proceedings document some of the tracking simulation work for the ATHENA detector proposal including geometry and material description, digitization, track finding/reconstruction, and performance checks. Following the EIC Detector Proposal Advisory Panel [1] recommendation to use the ECCE concept as a reference design for EIC Detector 1, the three proto-collaborations have been merged to continue the development of Detector 1 from reference to baseline. DD4hep, Acts, and EDM4hep will continue to be used as important components of the future simulation framework, making the development and experience from ATHENA quite valuable.

2 Geometry and Material Description

DD4hep is a comprehensive toolkit that provides a complete detector description for simulation, reconstruction, and analysis. It converts an easy-to-use compact detector description file in XML format to a ROOT TGeo-based generic model for geometry construction and visualization, and interfaces with Geant4 to perform simulations. The full implementation and documentation of the ATHENA detector geometry can be found in the code repository [13]. A detailed description of the tracking system can be found in Ref. [14]. Starting from the all-silicon tracker conceptual design (see Ref. [15]) used in the EIC Yellow Report, ATHENA developed a hybrid tracking system with mixed technologies including Monolithic Active Pixel Sensors (MAPS) and Micro Pattern Gas Detector (MPGD) technology.

Figure 1 shows the ATHENA central tracking system with realistic modeling of service and mechanical support structures. The core of the system is a set of MAPS detectors: six silicon disks in the forward (hadron-going) direction, five in the backward (electron-going) direction, with a span along the beam direction of +165 cm and -145 cm respectively, and five layers of silicon central barrels that cover pseudo-rapidity $|\eta| < 1.1$. In the backward/forward direction, there are two large Gas Electron Multiplier (GEM) rings to increase the detection area at relatively low cost. In the forward direction, a large micro-Resistive Well (μ RWell) disk is placed behind the dual Ring Imaging CHerenkov (dRICH) detector at $z = 335$ cm to increase tracking accuracy at this location. The backward direction has fewer disks to minimize material that electrons scattered in this direction go through. Two micromegas barrels (each contains two layers of

micromegas detectors) are put outside of the silicon barrels to provide additional tracking hits in the central region. A Low Gain Avalanche Detector (LGAD) is also included in the proposed tracking system to provide additional position and fast timing information. That particular subsystem is, however, not fully integrated into the reconstruction study presented here.

Figure 1: Illustration of the ATHENA central tracker in DD4hep. The axes are shown with units in cm. Note that the proposed dRICH detector, located between $z = 190$ to 330 cm, as well as other non-tracking subsystems are not shown.

All tracking detectors are implemented with detailed geometry and material thickness in DD4hep for use in Geant4 simulation and reconstruction with Acts. Segmentation for each detector surface is defined in the same compact XML files following the proposed detector feature sizes and resolutions. Acts can convert geometry descriptions from DD4hep detector volumes to Acts surface representations. The material thickness, however, needs to be manually assigned to Acts surfaces of choice. A full tutorial of this material assignment process can be found in Ref. [16]. In general, one needs to use Acts utilities to convert the detailed geometry in DD4hep into volume and surface descriptions, then go through layer volume boundaries to decide surfaces that the material will be mapped onto, and decide on a binning. In this study, we chose the Acts approaching layers to be just inwards of the sensitive tracking surfaces of the proposed detector, which all served as Acts mapping surfaces. In the case of the dRICH, additional surfaces were defined. The detector materials were then mapped onto the nearest mapping surfaces in generating the Acts material map. Typically, 36 bins in ϕ and 100 bins in z and R were found to give good results. This process was repeated with different binnings until the result was found to be in good agreement with Geant4 material scans using the geantino, which is a chargeless, massless, completely non-interacting virtual particle *c.f.* Fig. 2. The resulting material map was then used as input to Acts during reconstruction.

3 Track Reconstruction

3.1 Simulation Process

DD4hep takes initial particle information from either HepMC3 files [17] or from a particle gun. The simulated event information, including Monte Carlo (MC) truth particles and hits from each detector volume, were stored in ROOT files and served as the input to the Gaudi-based reconstruction framework called Juggler [18]. By default, Juggler calls the Acts-based Combinatorial Kalman Filter (CKF) for track finding

Figure 2: Material scan from the Acts material map (black) and from a geantino scan (red) as X/X_0 (top panel) and their ratio (bottom panel) versus pseudo-rapidity.

and reconstruction. Acts uses a simplified surface-based detector geometry to achieve faster navigation and reduce CPU time. Hits from the tracking detectors first went through a digitization step where hit positions were assigned to cell centers in the detector local coordinate system using input from the actual segmentation specified in DD4hep. Threshold cuts on timing and energy deposits or other response characteristics can also be applied on the detector hits at this stage, as needed. The digitized tracking hits from the detailed 3D detector geometry were then transformed into measurements on the Acts surfaces to perform CKF. Finally the reconstructed trajectories from CKF were matched with the Monte Carlo truth information to identify the reconstructed particles.

The initial and reconstructed particles, as well as their trajectories and hit information, were saved following structures defined by a PODIO-based [19] event data model called EICd [20], based on EDM4hep. By default, the tracking information was stored at the location of the collision vertex, including uncertainties along R and Z , azimuthal (θ) and polar (ϕ) angles, and charge to momentum ratios. Alternatively, one can also project the trajectories to any given detector surface to obtain the corresponding quantities along the track including the path-length. This functionality was used for several detector studies. The collision vertex was chosen to be at the nominal collision point for most studies presented here and more studies with an actual vertex distribution and reconstruction are planned for the future.

3.2 Single Particle Track Performance

Single π^+ events were used in the track performance study presented here. Only one outgoing π^+ was generated per event with uniformly chosen polar angle ϕ at any given momentum p and azimuthal angle θ . The MC truth particle information was used to create seeds for CKF in this study while the realistic seed finding algorithm is still under development. An event was considered to be properly reconstructed if there existed at least one reconstructed track within 5% in $\delta p/p$, 0.005 rad in θ , 0.03 rad in ϕ , and 3 mm in DCA_τ with respect to the initially generated quantities. The resolution of a given tracking variable is extracted as the standard deviation of a Gaussian fit to its residuals $\frac{recon-init}{init}$, where a single Gaussian provided an adequate parametrization. When this was not the case, a Gaussian was fitted to a truncated range around the central peak to make the fitting robust against tails. Figure 3 shows the tracking efficiency, angular distribution, and momentum and angle resolutions from a sample of single π^+ events. This process was repeated for different bins in η and p . Results were compared with the Yellow Report design resolutions, as

well as benchmarked against two other reconstruction packages, Fun4All [21] and LDT [22], as part of the validation of the ATHENA design concept and the entire simulation framework.

During the ATHENA proposal period, a material map was generated and the single particle tracking studies were performed every time the tracking system configuration was changed as part of the optimization process. Figure 4 shows the $\delta p/p$ performance of the final detector version (with code name DeathValley) that is reported in the ATHENA proposal and compares the performance with the physics requirements from the Yellow Report. In general, the ATHENA design performances meet or exceed the physics requirements of the Yellow Report. The very backward (electron-going) direction forms an exception, where no known tracking technology can currently meet the physics requirements even in a 3 T magnetic field. In the ATHENA design, only five disks were proposed in this direction (and hence at most five tracking hits are available) in a carefully studied optimization of the trade offs between traversed material and detector hit points. In the case of high-energy electrons, the Yellow Report requirements on momentum resolution may be reached by combination of the tracking information with the energy measurement using the proposed precision electromagnetic calorimetry (nEcal) located downstream of the tracking disks.

Limitations of the tracking studies presented here include, for example, that they are based on single particles without taking background hits into account and without realistic seeding and vertex reconstruction. For the anticipated collision rate (< 1 MHz) at the EIC design luminosities and for the proposed kinematics (center-of-mass energy < 144 GeV), the multiplicities in deep inelastic scatterings tend to be less than 10 within the detector acceptance [15]. Beam-induced backgrounds will contribute further hits and can thus affect the performance of the tracking algorithm. Further study of these effects is planned. The simulated performance is, furthermore, known to benefit from truth seeding for $p_T < 1$ GeV/c. With the assumption that at least five hits will be needed for a realistic track reconstruction, a particle in the central barrel region $|\eta| < 1.1$ will need to reach the sagitta barrel layer at $R = 18$ cm to satisfy this need. This radius corresponds to a minimum p_T of approximately $0.3 \cdot 3T \cdot 0.18\text{m}/2 \approx 80$ MeV/c. However, due to multiple scattering, the resolution distributions for $p_T < 400$ MeV/c are known to have non-Gaussian tails that underline the need for further study including backgrounds and more realistic seeding.

Figure 3: Track reconstruction resolutions from a sample of 10,000 single π^+ events generated with $\eta = 0.4 - 0.6$ and momenta p between 2 and 2.5 GeV/c.

4 Conclusions

The ATHENA detector proto-collaboration developed a comprehensive simulation and reconstruction software framework for EIC. It integrates widely-used software from the modern high-energy (nuclear) physics community to achieve high performance at manageable maintenance and development effort. Charged-particle tracking and reconstruction have been demonstrated during the proposal stage in simulations. Many of the associated software efforts, including DD4hep and Acts-based or related development, are

being adopted by the collaboration that is being formed around the EIC project detector. In particular, the software and simulation working groups of the new collaboration are working closely with the Acts developers towards a realistic tracking solution for EIC and also address important remaining open questions in the detector baseline design.

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Figure 4: The simulated momentum resolution $\delta p/p$ versus momentum for different η ranges as green markers and orange fitted curves. The blue dashed curves show the physics requirements from the Yellow Report. The dotted-dashed curves in red indicate the size of the constant term in the energy resolution for the proposed electromagnetic calorimeter in the electron-going direction [4]; this term limits the resolution that can ultimately be reached at high momenta in this acceptance region.